

ANALYSIS OF SOLVING IRRATIONAL EQUATIONS USING THE GEOGEBRA SOFTWARE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the introductory concepts of irrational equations, which are part of the chapter on irrational equations and inequalities in mathematics, along with the analysis of several examples related to the introduction of this topic. In addition, the article considers the analysis of these examples using the GeoGebra software.

The purpose of this analysis is to explain to general secondary school students the content and significance of the basic concepts that should be considered when solving irrational equations, using examples and diagrams.

Introduction

Today, along with the increasing demand for the development of the school mathematics curriculum, secondary school mathematics teachers face the pressing issue of organizing lessons in a way that is high-quality, effective, and prevents students from becoming bored with the subject [4,5,6].

At this point, it is worth mentioning Abu Rayhan Beruni's ideas on methods and ways of acquiring scientific knowledge. According to him, when teaching students, attention should be paid to the following:

- Do not bore the learner.
- Avoid teaching the same things or the same subject repeatedly.

Taking these points into account, this article examines the topic "**Simple Irrational Equations and Their Systems**" in mathematics for 10th-grade students in secondary school, analyzing several conveniences and challenges in teaching this topic.

Examples related to finding the domain of definition to determine solutions or to prove that solutions do not exist:

Example 1:

$$\sqrt{2x-3} + \sqrt{1-x} = 5 \quad [1,2,8].$$

$$\sqrt{2x-3} + \sqrt{1-x} = 5$$

Let an equation be given. Before finding the solution of this equation, we first determine its **domain of definition**.

$$\begin{aligned} 2x-3 & \geq 0 & x & \geq 3, x < 2 \\ 1-x & \geq 0 & & \end{aligned}$$

From the diagram above and the previously determined domain of definition, it is clear that there is no domain where this equation has a solution.

Now, we consider this equation as the equality of two functions and check whether these functions intersect using the GeoGebra software. To do this, we first rewrite the equation as

$$\sqrt{2x-3} = 5 - \sqrt{1-x}$$

in this form, $y = \sqrt{2x-3}$, $y = 5 - \sqrt{1-x}$ consider them as functions, and plot their graphs using the software.

Indeed, as can be seen from the graphs, these two functions do not intersect, and therefore the solution set of this equation is the **empty set**.

$\sqrt{f(x)} = g(x)$ **Examples of equations in the form of and their solutions:**

$$2\sqrt{x+5} = x+2 \quad [1,6].$$

Solution: To find the solution of this equation, we first determine its domain of definition.

$$x+2 \geq 0 \quad x \geq -2$$

$$x+5 \geq 0 \quad x \geq -5$$

Next, we square both sides of the equation.

$$2\sqrt{x+5} = x+2$$

$$4x+20 = x^2 + 4x+4$$

$$x^2 = 16$$

$$x_{1,2} = \pm 4$$

According to the domain of definition, the solution of the equation will be equal to .

Now, to solve this equation, we consider it as the equality of two functions, just as before, and analyze the graphs using the GeoGebra software.

$$y = 2\sqrt{x+5}$$

$$y = x + 2$$

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